

MEDICAL SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES IN SELECTED HOSPITALS IN THE DUTSE LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, JIGAWA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study assessed the medical solid waste management methods in Dutse General and Sambo hospitals in Dutse, Jigawa State. However, medical solid wastes expose health workers, patients, waste handlers, and the general public to health risks. The method employed use of questionnaire administration, in-depth interviews, and observation as the techniques for data collection to capture medical solid waste management methods in selected hospitals in Dutse including the types of medical solid waste generated in these hospitals, the current medical solid waste management methods, and the effect of medical solid waste among waste handlers, patients, and caregivers in the study area. A total of 94 copies of the questionnaire were used. Purposive sampling was used to select waste handlers. Results on medical solid waste show that sharp/infectious waste is the most common medical solid waste generated in the two study areas. This study aimed to determine the availability of storage containers and separations of sharps/infectious materials, absence of color coding, central storage facilities, and recycling of medical waste in Dutse General Hospital (DGH). In both study areas, incineration, burning, and burying were adopted as waste treatment methods. Waste transportation was mainly performed using carts at SHL and open vehicles at DGH. Medical solid waste disposal methods are primarily by open dumping and burning at both DGH and SHL. Similarly, healthcare/waste workers are at risk of injuries from sharp objects (needles, broken bottles, etc.) as the effect of medical solid waste which has the highest mean value at DGH and is ranked first. At SHL, psychological impacts (stress and anxiety) and allergies are the effects of medical solid waste with the highest mean value and are ranked first. In conclusion, General and Sambo hospitals have been conducting solid waste management practices. It is recommended that better modern techniques should be introduced in the selected hospitals by the management to protect the management, health care workers, and public health from diseases. In addition, the management of the two hospitals should improve their medical solid waste disposal methods. However, further study on the effects of the medical solid waste from the two hospitals on the environment (soil, water, and air) is recommended.

Keywords: Management, Practices, Hospitals, Medical Waste, Solid Waste.

1. INTRODUCTION

Environmentalists and informed residents in Nigeria voice considerable apprehension regarding insufficient waste management in hospitals and other health care facilities. Hospitals are health care institutions that deliver medical services, whereas health care establishments directly manage public health through patient care. It also guarantees a sanitary and healthful environment for employees and community members. In other words, health care activities protect the environment, cure patients, and save lives. However, during their operations, they generate medical solid waste, 20% of which puts humans at risk of infections, trauma, chemical or radiation exposure, and occasionally even death (WHO, 2018). Radar et al. (2018) described several hospital waste, including sharps, human tissues, body parts, and other disposable but infectious materials referred to as "Medical Solid

Waste." The problem of improving the management of medical solid waste is receiving increasing attention worldwide because health care institutions generate tons of medical solid waste each year.

According to Bhangu et al. (2023), wastes are materials that individuals would wish to get rid of, even if doing so costs money. Waste is a necessary byproduct of human activity, but it is also the outcome of ineffective production methods, the ongoing creation of which depletes key resources. Any material that is rejected by society's material flow pattern is considered solid waste, whereas management is the prudent use of a means to an end. With the increasing urbanization of the world, the possible health risk of improper waste disposal is a serious concern (WHO, 2018). We refer to all wastes created during medical or diagnostic procedures as "medical waste." Between 75% and 90% of hospital waste is equivalent to garbage from homes or businesses and poses no unique risks. Refuse from health care centers can be collected, recycled, and processed in the same way as domestic waste. Particular or hazardous medical waste refers to the remaining 10%–25%. This type of waste raises health concerns (World Health Organization, 2018).

Healthcare institutions of all kinds define medical solid waste as any waste they produce during the diagnosis, treatment, or immunization of humans or animals, as well as related biological research, production, or testing (2020). According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2020), medical solid waste is any waste produced while providing healthcare services and can include a wide range of items, such as radioactive materials, body parts, soiled dressings, used needles and syringes, diagnostic tests, and medical gadgets.

The production of harmful sulfide and methane gases via open-air storage, the formation of heavy metals in landfill leachate through leaching (You et al., 2020), and the release of carcinogenic polychlorinated biphenyls and dioxins during incineration (Minoglu et al. 2020) are all associated with the inappropriate disposal of medical solid wastes (Emenike et al. 2017).

Medical solid waste management (MSWM) in developing countries has become an issue of global significance (Sanjeev et al., 2020). With the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, we have learned how fragile medical and solid waste management chains are and how this could lead to an increasing environmental pollution scenario (You et al. 2020). Sanjeev et al. (2020) noted a surge in the creation of medical solid waste from positive cases. Nigeria and other developing countries focus on two interconnected but crucial issues: waste management and sanitation (Singh et al., 2022). Medical solid wastes are hazardous because they contain radioactive materials, dangerous chemicals, and pathogenic microbiological elements (Khan et al. 2019). They may also change microbial ecology, resulting in resistance to antibiotics. (Onu et al., 2023).

Unfortunately, practical information about the implications of inadequate management of medical solid wastes is lacking. Coker et al. (as cited in Isyaku, 2015) reported a near-total absence of institutional arrangements for medical solid wastes in Nigeria.

Population growth in the Dutse Local Government Area has led to a rising demand for medical services. Consequently, this surge is increasing the generation of medical solid waste, raising the potential for environmental and human harm. Therefore, it is crucial to assess the medical and solid waste management practices in hospitals located within the Dutse Local Government Area, Jigawa State.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The study area is Dutse, the capital city of Jigawa State, Nigeria. The map indicates that the study area is situated between 11°43'20"N and 11°43'28"N and 9°18'40"E and 9°23'20"E (Figure 3.1). It covers an area of approximately 420 square miles (1,089-kilometre square (Kura et al., 2023). This area is primarily urban, with several key landmarks and facilities, including Dutse General Hospital, a major healthcare facility in the region, Sambo Hospital Limited, another healthcare center providing medical services, and Saminu Tower, a notable landmark in the area. State Library, Federal University Dutse, and a State Secretariat, which is an administrative building. The study area is well-connected by main roads and minor roads/streets, making it accessible for transportation and waste management activities (Kura et al., 2023).

The dump sites are within the same general area, as shown in the second map. The dump site coordinates are approximately 9°21'44"E to 9°22'8"E and 11°43'20"N to 11°43'28"N. The dump sites are relatively close to the study area, likely within a 1-2 km radius, based on the map scale (1:51,245). It is accessible via minor roads connect it to the main roads leading to the study area. The proximity of the dump sites to the study area raises concerns about potential environmental and health impacts, especially if waste management practices are inadequate.

The study area includes Dutse General DGH and Sambo Hospital SHL, which are critical public health facilities. Improper waste management in the area could pose risks to these facilities, such as infection spread or contamination of medical supplies. Improper waste disposal could affect the Indian Quarters and other residential zones near the study area, leading to health risks such as respiratory issues, water contamination, and vector-borne diseases. The proximity of the dump site to the study area raises concerns about air pollution (from burning waste), water contamination (if waste leaches into groundwater or nearby water bodies), and soil degradation. The presence of minor roads near the dump site that waste transportation might pass through populated areas, increasing the risk of littering and environmental pollution. The proximity of the dump site to health care facilities, residential areas, and educational institutions underscores the importance of addressing waste management challenges to protect public health and the environment.

Figure 1: Map of Dutse

Source: Extracted from the Administrative Map of Jigawa State.

2. METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

1. Reconnaissance survey

A reconnaissance survey was conducted to familiarize the researcher with the study area. The researcher also used this avenue to establish a good relationship with the hospital's staff, cleaners, and sanitary workers and solicit their support for the research.

2. Research design

This study employed a descriptive survey design, which is a type of non-experimental research design aimed at systematically collecting and analyzing data to describe a specific population's characteristics, behaviors, or attitudes. This study focused on assessing medical solid waste management practices in selected hospitals in Dutse, Jigawa State, Nigeria. The descriptive survey design was an appropriate choice for this study, as it allowed the researcher to systematically collect and analyze data on medical solid waste management practices in the selected hospitals (Creswell, 2014). By combining quantitative and qualitative methods, this study provided a detailed and nuanced understanding of the types of waste generated, current management practices, and their effects on patients, waste handlers, and caregivers. This design laid the foundation for actionable recommendations to improve hospital waste management practices.

3. Instrument used for data collection

a. Questionnaire

A questionnaire is a research tool made up of a set of questions intended to elicit information from respondents (McLeod, 2018). The questionnaire used in this study was adopted from Isyaku (2015), a previous study on medical solid waste management. However, the study was modified to align with the specific objectives of this research and the unique context of the selected health care facilities. Some questions were adjusted to reflect the current waste management practices in the study area.

b. In-depth interview

In-depth interviewing is a qualitative research method that entails conducting detailed individual interviews with a limited number of participants to gain insights into their views on a specific concept, program, or situation (Boyce, 2016). The interview participants were five (5) patients and five caregivers (5) to the two hospitals to ensure a balance between obtaining a broad range of perspectives and managing the depth of each interview. A total of 10 participants were interviewed.

4. Sample size and sampling technique used

The objective of this study is to assess the methods of managing medical solid waste in Dutse. A public general hospital and a private commercial hospital were considered for a comprehensive understanding. Dutse General Hospital and Sambo Hospital Limited were used.

Purposive sampling was used in this study. Sometimes referred to as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling, it depends on the researcher's judgment in choosing the study units (individuals, cases/organizations, events, or data points) (Pandey et al. 2021).

Data for the study were analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 22.0. The analysis was conducted according to the following objectives.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1 Demographic characteristic of the respondents at Dutse General Hospital and Sambo Hospitals Limited.

This section presents the demographic and socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents in the two selected hospitals. Table 1 presents the demographic characteristics of the respondents based on gender, age, marital

status, educational status, and years of experience in waste handling. The majority (71.25% and 64.29%) of the respondents were males, while the least (28.75% and 35.71%) were females at both DGH and SHL, respectively. This implies that more men are employed in the two hospitals than their female counterparts. This could mean that no gender equality or balance exists in the employment of waste managers in the two hospitals. If there is a gender imbalance among the employed waste managers, it could be attributed to the tedious nature of the work or its hazardous nature. Hospital waste handling roles often involve physical labor and exposure to various hazards, such as biohazardous materials and chemicals. Historically, societal perceptions of strength and suitability for manual labor have led males to predominantly occupy these roles.

Table 1 Demographic characteristics of the respondents

Hospitals	Use General Hospital	Sambo Hospital, Ltd.	Frequency	Percentage %
Gender	Frequency	Percentage %	Frequency	Percentage%
Male	57	71.25	9	64.29
Female	23	28.75	5	35.71
Total	80	100.00	14	100.00
Age				
20-30	11	13.75	4	28.57
31-40	48	60.0	7	50.0
41-50	18	22.50	3	21.43
51 and above	3	3.75	0	0.00
Total	80	100.00	14	100.00

Source: Field survey conducted in 2024

2. Medical Solid Waste Management Method

This section presents findings on the knowledge, attitude, and current practices of MSWM in the selected hospitals. The questionnaire was administered to the waste workers to examine the involvement, knowledge, and current practices of medical solid waste management, including the availability of storage containers, color coding, separation, and central waste storage facility.

Waste handlers are involved in the handling of medical waste

Figure 2 shows how the waste handlers are involved in handling medical waste. Many studies have proved that in some hospitals, waste handlers are not fully involved in the handling of waste. However, in the case of Dutse General Hospital and Sambo Hospital Ltd, the majority (64%) of the respondents ticked Yes, implying or agreeing that they are fully involved in waste handling. This provided the basis for further analysis of the study objectives.

Figure 2 Involvement in waste handling

Source: Field Survey (2024)

Knowledge of medical solid waste management

There is also the issue of knowledge of medical solid waste management, which is presented in Figure 2. Because of the occupation that involves medical solid waste, there is a need for waste handlers to know about medical waste management, which would make them carry out management practices effectively. The sources of this knowledge could be experience about waste handling, seminars, and training. The majority (72%) of the respondents ticked Yes, indicating that they know about waste management. Only 28% ticked “No,” implying that

They do not know medical waste, which is insignificant compared with the majority’s opinion.

Figure 3 Knowledge of medical waste management

Source: Field Survey (2024)

Self-acquired training and knowledge

Self-acquired training and knowledge were important to this study, in which the respondents provided information regarding self-acquired training and knowledge. This is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Self-Acquired Training and Knowledge

Source: Field Survey (2024)

The majority (53%) ticked No, meaning that acquired knowledge and training regarding handling waste is not self against the least (47%) that ticked Yes. Waste handling is a sensitive aspect of medical waste that requires training by hospital management to avoid mishandling of medical waste. Therefore, the majority has a valid opinion regarding self-acquired training and knowledge of medical waste management.

Availability of storage containers, color coding, separation, and central waste storage facility at both the DGH and the SHL

Table 2 shows the availability of storage containers, container coding, waste separation, and central storage facility. All the respondents in both DGH and SHL 80 and 14, representing 100%, attested that the health care facilities have waste storage containers in different units/departments. This implies that there is a high level of compliance with the provision of containers in the healthcare facility, which prevents the indiscriminate dumping of medical solid wastes in wards and clinics.

Observations around the facilities also confirmed this, as every facility visited has one form of container or the other for waste collection, and this falls within the acceptable standards recommended by the WHO (2018). Some health care facilities in Nigeria also use inappropriate containers, such as plastic bags, paper bags, or cardboard, to collect medical waste (Coker, 2009). This statement was also the same in the study area, where plastic bags, paper bags, and nylon were used to collect medical solid waste.

The table also shows that all the respondents representing 100% reported that the containers have color coding at SHL and DGH, respectively, indicating that there were no color coding practices for receptacles in their hospitals for medical waste management as the majority of the respondents (78.75%) reported that no such practice is done in their healthcare facility. The report shows a low level of compliance with color-coding practices at the DGH.

This is confirmed by Olubukola's (2009) findings in Lagos that healthcare waste management practices are marred with poor color-coding practices and a lack of instructive posters on waste segregation and disposal of general wastes in Nigerian public hospitals. According to Ndidi et al. (2009) and Abah and Ohimain (2011), the segregation of waste in marked color-coded receptacles would result in a clean medical waste stream that could be easily, safely, and cost-effectively managed through recycling, composting, and landfilling.

Table 2 Storage container availability, color coding, separation, and central waste storage facility

Hospital	YES		NO	
	Frequency	Percentage %	Frequency	Percentage %
DGH	80	100.00	0	0.0
SHL	14	100.0	0	0
Color coding				
DGH	17	21.25	63	78.75
SHL	14	100.0	0	0
Waste separation				
DGH	73	91.25	7	8.75
SHL	14	100.0	0	0
Central waste storage				
DGH	0	0.00	80	100.0
SHL	14	100.0	0	0.00

Source: Field survey conducted in 2024

The table further revealed that 91.25% and 100% of the respondents from DGH and SHL, respectively, indicated that there were separations of waste for sharps or infectious materials in their hospitals. This study reveals that the facility has a high regard/compliance for the segregation of sharps/infectious waste. Coker et al. (2009) reported that there was no proper segregation in the Ibadan healthcare facilities in Nigeria. The study team had to implement waste sorting and segregation at the source by providing coded separate receptacles for each identified medical waste component. Improperly disposed of hazardous HCW (such as syringes and needles in the absence of sterilization) can cause Hepatitis B, C, and HIV infections (WHO, 2002) and pose indirect risks to humans through direct environmental effects by contaminating soil and groundwater (Abah and Ohimain, 2011).

From the observations around the facility, containers of varying sizes existed, and it was observed that anatomical waste, such as human body parts, organs, aborted fetuses, placenta, and tissues, was prevalent in the facility surveyed, but the separation was not done using the right color-coded containers/receptacles. The facility also engaged in the source separation of sharp objects, including needles, scalpels, and operating blades that are segregated in the health care facility. Sharp/injection boxes are used in various wards, clinics, and laboratories.

Table 2 further shows that 100% of the respondents reported that there is a central waste storage facility at SHL, while 100% of the respondents reported that there was no central waste storage facility at DGH, where all gathered wastes from all the units/departments are stored before transportation to the final destination for disposal. This implies that the DGH lacks a good waste collection strategy to tackle the medical waste menace. This could be because it is government-owned, and most government health care facilities face the challenges of inadequate infrastructural facilities. In addition, for research, the DGH may see the need to put all hands-on desks toward their medical solid waste management. Coker et al. (2009) reported insecure and inadequate central storage facilities in Nigeria. Most hospitals in Nigeria had no special place for the storage of medical waste (Coker et al., 2009). Algo and Kocasoy (2008) also reported the unsecured location of storage depots at the Ibn-Nafis Hospital in Istanbul, Turkey. It has limited access; it is easily accessible to personnel responsible for waste handling.

Treatment of Medical Solid Wastes at Dutse General Hospital and Sambo Hospital Limited

Table 3 presents the waste treatment methods adopted at both DGH and SHL before disposal. This reveals that the autoclaving of waste is not done at health care facilities. Autoclaving is a pretreatment practice used to treat samples from highly infectious patients before disposal. Treatment of medical waste using autoclaving at DGH and SHL is absent because none of the respondents (0.0%) reported the existence of autoclaving in their health care facilities. This implies that this practice is very poor or absent in the facility, exposing the laboratory staff and other waste handlers to a high risk of contact with highly infectious wastes. Isyaku (2015) also reported that autoclaving is still in its infancy in Zaria.

The table also shows that 85.0% of the DGH and 100% of the SHL respondents reported that the practice of incinerating waste exists in the hospitals, whereas 15.0% of the DGH and 0.0% of the SHL respondents reported that it is absent. This result shows that incineration as a practice is present at both DGH and SHL due to the high response from the respondents. As a result, incineration prevents the waste handlers and medical staff from exposure to infections through contact with hazardous waste.

Healthcare waste incineration was found to be a common practice in the surveyed healthcare facilities. Most of the incineration technologies in healthcare facilities were found to be in obsolete condition and operated in a rudimentary fashion or were simply nonfunctional. Incinerators are poorly designed and often have operational problems (Coker et al., 2009).

Table 3 Method of Waste Treatment at both DGH and SHL

Hospitals Treatment Method	DGH				SHL			
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Autoclaving	0	0.00	80	100.0	0	0.00	14	100.0
Incinerating hazardous waste	68	85.0	12	15.0	14	100.0	0	0.00
Burying	72	90.0	8	10.0	0	0.00	14	100.0
Use of chemical disinfectants	0	0.00	80	100.0	9	64.28	5	34.71

Source: Field survey conducted in 2024

Transportation of Medical Solid Wastes for Disposal at Dutse General Hospital and Sambo Hospital Limited

Table 4 presents the waste transportation method for final disposal. Ogbonna et al. (2010), Ogbonna (2011), Oke (2008), and Olubukola (2009) argued that the method of transporting waste of all kinds to the final destination is an integral part of achieving proper and sustainable waste management. The authors specifically pointed out the effect of hazardous waste if it is not transported using proper methods. The effect could be on both the surroundings and healthcare workers, especially waste handlers, who are at the highest risk of occupational injuries.

Table 4 shows that the use of open vehicles is the most dominant and common method of transporting medical waste at DGH to its final destination for disposal, with 54 representing (67.50%) of the respondents. Only occasionally (25.0%) did the respondents report that carts are used to transport medical solid waste for disposal at DGH.

This implies that the hospital is at risk of environmental pollution and occupational health risks due to the poor transportation of medical solid waste. This finding is in agreement with that of Isyaku (2015), who reported that 80% of all waste in Nigeria is transported using carts and other open means due to inadequate waste transportation facilities in Nigerian healthcare centers. The author attributed this to a corrupt government system at all levels and in most Nigerian government establishments.

Table 4: Method of transporting medical solid waste for disposal at both DGH and SHL

HOSPITALS Transportation method	DGH		SHL	
	Frequency	Percentage %	Frequency	Percentage %
Open Vehicles	54	67.50	3	21.43
Trucks	6	7.50	0	0.00
Carts	20	25.00	11	78.57
Trolleys	0	0.00	0	0.00

Enclosed compaction	0	0.00	0	0.00
Total	80	100.00	14	100.00

Source: Field survey conducted in 2024

The table further shows that the use of carts (78.57%) is the most dominant and common method of transporting medical solid waste at SHL to its final destination for disposal. Only a few respondents (21.43 %) reported that open vehicles are also used to transport medical solid waste for disposal at the SHL. This implies that the hospital is not at risk of environmental pollution due to poor transportation of medical solid waste. This finding is in agreement with that of Saidu (2018), who reported that 70% of medical solid waste in Nigeria is transported using open vehicles and carts but not the recommended enclosed compaction vehicle.

Method of Medical Solid Waste Disposal at Dutse General Hospital and Sambo Hospital Limited

The method of medical waste disposal is presented in Table 5. It was reported that the method employed by DGH for medical solid waste disposal shows that according to (73.75%) of the respondents was open dumpsite, burning (22.5), and burying (3.75). Burning (78.57) and open dumping (21.43) are the final waste destinations at SHL.

Table 5: Method of Medical Solid Waste Disposal at both DGH and SHL

Hospitals Method of waste disposal	DGH		SHL	
	Frequency	Percentage %	Frequency	Percentage %
Open dumping	59	73.75	3	21.43
Landfill	0	0.00	0	0.00
Shredding	0	0.00	0	0.00
Burying	3	3.75	0	0.00
Burning	18	22.5	11	78.57
Total	80	100.0	14	100.0

Source: Field survey conducted in 2024

This implies that open dumping and burning are the most common waste disposal practices at DGH, while burning and open dumping are the most adopted methods at SHL. The results highlight the complexity and diversity of opinions regarding waste disposal methods. These findings are consistent with those of Isyaku (2015), who affirmed that open dumping and burial are the most common methods of medical waste disposal at ABUTH and ABUHS. Oke (2008) also confirmed that most healthcare establishments in Nigeria use open disposal as the final disposal method. This result also supports the findings of Ogbonna (2011), who reported that open dumping and burning are the most common waste disposal practices in Nigeria, regardless of whether the waste is hazardous or not.

An in-depth interview with a patient was conducted on the methods of waste transport and disposal. The discussant said,

P1, 2, 5,9,10 “What I see mostly done to remove waste is burning.” This is related to medical waste that can be burned. Other waste, such as broken bottles and syringes, I don’t know what they will do with them. However, I believe they have a method of removing such solid medical waste”

Similarly, a caregiver commented on the same issue regarding the method of medical solid waste transportation and disposal. He said,

P3, 4, 8: "When the incinerator is filled up, I see trucks moving the waste away. I think they have places where they dump the waste or bury it." I have no in-depth knowledge of this.

4. Conclusion

According to the study, the most common type of trash generated at DGH is sharp/infectious waste, whereas at SHL. There were efforts to separate infectious materials or sharps and the presence of storage containers, and serious flaws were found, such as a lack of color coding, centralized storage facilities, and recycling programs. This observation underscores the urgent need to improve waste segregation and waste management practices in health care settings to reduce health risks.

The primary disposal methods used by DGH and SHL for waste treatment were incineration, burying, and landfilling, with open dumping and burning being the most common. This emphasizes a reliance on simple and sometimes dangerous waste management techniques, which could seriously endanger both the environment and human health. The study highlights the need for urgently updated, safer waste treatment and disposal techniques in health care settings.

This study found that medical solid waste poses serious health risks, especially to trash handlers and health care personnel. Sharp object injuries were the most frequent health risk at the DGH, but psychological effects (stress and anxiety) and allergies (with the highest mean value of 4.33) were more common at the SHL. These findings highlight the risks to occupational health of healthcare workers and support better safety procedures and preventative measures to protect their health and welfare.

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